

EROSION AS AN IMPORTANT FACTOR LEADING TO THE DESTRUCTION OF ELEMENTS IN INDUSTRIAL BOILERS AND INDUSTRIAL GAS INSTALLATIONS OPERATING WITH NATURAL GAS

Vasileva V.

M.Sc

4004 Plovdiv, Bulgaria

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Abstract

The scientific report analyzes erosion as a factor leading to the destruction of the main machine parts from which industrial boilers and industrial gas installations are built. The different types of erosion and the reasons for their occurrence are shown, as well as the dependence of some types of erosion on the resulting destruction.

Keywords: Reliability of industrial gas installations, erosion of machine parts of boilers and gas installations, cavitation erosion

1. Introduction

Erosion is a complex concept that includes several components leading to the destruction of structural machine elements in industrial boilers and industrial gas plants operating on natural gas. These components usually cause surface damage to the elements, which occurs as a result of the dynamic movement of the various fluid streams used, including liquids and gas. In some isolated cases, an erosion effect can also occur as a result of dynamically moving streams of solid particles or electrical discharges. In most cases, in the process of erosion, an intense destruction of the material occurs, and together with this, phenomena such as pitting, caverns and shells occur on the walls of the metal and especially on the pipes of the tube bundle of the boilers.

Erosion mainly occurs as a result of the destruction of the various metal surfaces used in boilers and gas piping systems under the influence of repeated shocks of a flow of water or natural gas.

Destructions as a result of erosion lead to the removal of machine elements from service significantly earlier than the period of normal operation determined by their manufacturer. For this reason, the aim is to manage the erosion process so that it is as weak as possible and its influence is significantly reduced.

2. Main types of erosion

In determining the main types of erosion, a significant influence is exerted by the principle according to which the corresponding type of erosion is the result of the external conditions of impact.

There are four main types of erosion:

- Gas erosion
- Cavitation erosion
- Abrasive erosion
- Electrical erosion

Gas erosion is the phenomenon in which the destruction of machine elements in industrial boilers and gas installations operating with natural gas is under the influence of the mechanical and thermal forces of gas molecules.

Abrasive erosion is manifested in the destruction of machine parts and components, through the damage occurring as a result of the impact of small solid particles.

Cavitation erosion damages metal elements, as a result of the micro-shock impact that occurs when the particles of the respective fluid move..

Electrical erosion is the destruction of metal elements under the influence of electrical forces. As a result of systematic research and study, a sufficiently correct table for classifying erosion can be compiled (Figure 1).

Figure 1

The erosional damage observed during the studies very rarely follows a single mechanism. The mechanical-chemical form appears as one of the most widespread forms of destruction of machine elements of boilers and industrial gas installations, which use liquid and gaseous fluids in the process of their work, as well as often occurring flows of solid particles. A microimpact erosion mechanism can occur in cases where the surface of a material in a gas or liquid stream or solid particles is subjected to local impacts of an impulsive nature. The energy of these impacts is sufficient to cause plastic deformation, structural or phase transformations in the corresponding microvolumes.

3. Cavitation Erosion

During the operation of industrial boilers and gas installations, they are subjected to micro-shock effects. This loading is associated with the appearance of plastic deformation, which is characterized by distributed concentration and volume non-uniformity. These shock loads affect the contact surfaces and change the properties of the metal elements (pipes, casing, etc.). As a result of this impact, the formation of microcracks begins, which at a later stage pass into destruction zones and often lead to the detachment of whole pieces from the attacked surface.

The occurrence and development of these cracks depends on the strength and energy of the impact, the

structure of the metal and its chemical composition. The most important role in this negative process is the temperature, because the metal parts in industrial boilers work under constant heating to high temperatures.

In industrial gas installations for natural gas, there is a similar effect, as the bonds between the metal particles weaken and the metal particles are carried away by the gas flow. The destruction of the surface layer in the gas flow is the result of the mechanical impact of the flow, its aerodynamic force and the abrasive action of the solid particles.

In industrial boilers, a process of hydroerosion is observed, since they work with a dynamic flow of liquid fluid (water). The main type of destruction of the metal in this case is mechano-chemical, since it occurs at a relatively low flow rate. However, it develops within acceptable limits, since the erosion is not high and is stable in its manifestation. When increasing the water flow rate in the boiler, micro-impact damage occurs, which in cavitation conditions increases its impact on the metal. This cavitation is general, when the formation of vapor-gas layers occurs as a result of the pressure drop in the entire flow, or local, when the pressure drops in certain places in the water space of the boiler and the installation adjacent to it.

Figure 2

Figure 2 shows the dependence of the intensity of surface destruction of metal parts during hydroerosion on the speed of water flow in industrial boilers.

Hydroerosion during cavitation manifests itself particularly strongly in certain places in the boiler and has a destructive effect on the main metal elements of its construction.

Depending on the flow conditions of the fluid (natural gas or water), pressure and temperature, metal elements and details can work in non-stationary conditions. In these cases, the process of destruction as a result of erosion can be divided into several stages that depend on the combination of different phenomena.

Critical values of particle impact energy can be reached for any material. These values depend on the composition of the abrasive particles that act on the metal and the environment in which the deformation processes begin to develop and in depth of the affected metal zone.

The main thing in this case is the destruction caused by the micro-impacts of the particles, and the mechanical and chemical destruction are concomitant phenomena. The intensity of destruction increases sharply, as a result of which the number of new particles formed, separated from the surface of the attacked metal zone, increases.

In conclusion, it can be concluded that erosion is an extremely harmful phenomenon when using pipelines and installations for natural gas and industrial boilers. Therefore, it is necessary to make an accurate analysis of the nature of the occurring erosion processes and to draw up the necessary plans to prevent or greatly reduce the impact of the various elements of erosion in the process of operation of industrial boilers and gas installations for natural gas.

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